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Optimization of Sea Defense Strategy Through Operation of the Hospital Auxiliary Vessel to Support National Defense

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Abstract

The dynamics of the strategic environment at the global, regional and national levels give rise to various types of threats, both military and non-military threats, encouraging to optimize the Indonesian Sea Defense Strategy (SDS) which has the characteristics of an archipelagic country. In accordance with peaceful conditions, the optimization of SDS is more appropriate if it is directed at the military operations other than war, which in this study focuses on the operation of Hospital Auxiliary Vessel (HAV). There were problems related to the ineffective HAV operation, because it was used for material transportation and border operations. Its operation doesn't provide public health services in isolated, frontier and outermost areas. The purpose of this study is to analyze and explain the implementation and to formulate strategies to optimize SDS through the operation of HAV in order to support national defense. The research used is descriptive qualitative with a phenomenological approach. The data were obtained from interviews at the Ministry of Defense, Ministry of Health and Indonesian Navy Headquarters. The results of the studied that SDS through the operation of HAV was implemented quite well, but the operating time often exceeded the initial plan due to the limited number of HAV and their crew. The conclusion from this research is necessary for optimization of SDS which is emphasized on the Sea Control Strategy in accordance with the strategy development on the ends, ways and means components.

Keywords: Sea Defense Strategy (SDS), Hospital Auxiliary Vessel (HAV), Optimization, Sea Control Strategy

1. Introduction

The dynamics of the strategic environment at the global, regional, and national levels produce various threats that encourages the need to optimize the Indonesian Sea Defense Strategy (SDS). Those threats can be classified as threats of a military and non-military nature. This is in accordance with the explanation in Law Number 3 of 2003 concerning State Defense, which states that there are two types of threats to the country's sovereignty, namely military and non-military threats. Military threats are threats that use organized armed force and are considered capable of endangering the sovereignty and territorial integrity of a country, as well as the safety of citizens and the entire nation. Non-military threats are essentially threats that do not use force of arms, however, they can endanger the sovereignty and territorial integrity of a country, as well as the safety of the entire nation. These threats include radicalism, separatism, social conflicts, disease outbreaks, cyber attacks, exploitation of natural resources and so on.

The military threat to Indonesian sovereignty stems primarily from China's violations of territory in the North Natuna Sea. Non-military threats include the spread of covid-19, which is very detrimental to the state and all Indonesian people; rampant illegal fishing activities; border disputes, and public welfare problems in border areas.

The non-military threat in the form of the spread of covid-19 is a threat whose resolution is mandated by the state to the medical team who handles it directly at locations where the virus spreads. The aim of these efforts is to prevent the spread of Covid-19 from spreading and to minimize the number of victims due to the virus infection. Non-military threats in the form of illegal fishing activities and a crisis in the welfare and health of coastal communities can be resolved by optimizing SDS.

SDS which has been implemented in Indonesia since 2004 is the Archipelago Sea Defense Strategy (ASDS). The target of the ASDS is to prevent parties from disturbing the sovereignty of the country and the territorial integrity of the Republic of Indonesia by sea. The ASDS is an integral part of the Archipelago's Defense Strategy which is laid out on three interrelated main pillars, namely the defense and security system of the universal people, defense in depth and deterrence (Herdiawan et al., 2020; Mustari et al., 2018).

ASDS is a translation of the TNI AL doctrine "Eka Sasana Jaya" which is used as a guide in carrying out the duties and functions of the Indonesian Navy. This is carried out to overcome maritime threats, domestic security disturbances, and armed rebellion in the territory of the Republic of Indonesia in order to create a safe and controlled national jurisdiction sea condition. To realize these various goals, the ASDS was implemented. Where the ASDS consists of Deterrence Strategy, Layer Defense Strategy and Sea Control Strategy (Mustari et al., 2018).

Basically, the ASDS is a framework for implementing the three general roles of the Navy as the main component of sea defense, namely roles in the military, diplomacy and police. The role in the military realm relates to the empowerment of state forces at sea in order to achieve a conducive maritime situation, build a strong maritime force, and ensure the creation of border security and the entire national marine area. The role of diplomacy is manifested in a variety of activities that support cooperation with other countries, such as conducting joint exercises, exchanging military members, and participating in multilateral activities. The third role is the role of the police, namely the role of the Navy which is held in peaceful conditions in the form of activities to safeguard national waters, law enforcement at sea, and the implementation of Military Operations Other Than War (MOOTW) (Mustari et al., 2018)

According to Hidayat (2015), the threats that often arise in peaceful conditions are non-military threats. Therefore, the role of Indonesian Navy that needs to be developed is the police role, especially in the form of MOTW. This role is carried out with the aim of supporting the government in overcoming domestic crises, including poverty, hunger, health crises and so on. In order for the implementation of the role of the police in the form of MOTW to be optimal, it requires the completeness and adequacy of the Indonesian Navy's defense equipment, including in terms of the availability of Hospital Auxiliary Vessel (HAV).

However, it is known that currently the number of HAV owned by the Indonesian Navy is only three units consisting of KRI dr. Soeharso (SHS) -990, KRI Semarang-594, and KRI dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo-991. According to President Joko Widodo's statement as conveyed by representatives of PT PAL Indonesia as the maker of the KRI Semarang-594 and KRI Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo-991, the number is still very small and Indonesia needs at least five more HAVs (Dewanti, 2019). According to the Indonesian Navy's point of view, TNI Major General M. Sabrar Fadhilah, who served as the Head of the Indonesian Navy Information Center in 2018, stated that in theory there is no clear reference regarding the ideal number of HAV for Indonesia which has a very large water area. However, at least, Indonesia must have 10 HAV in order to cover this vast water area (Hadi & Persada, 2018).

The number of HAV is considered unable to reach all people living in disadvantaged, frontier and outermost areas (3T areas). In addition, it was also found that the operation of the HAV was intended for missions other than humanitarian missions and the operation targeting model still referred to data collection on the number of people who were sick and needed health service assistance, not for the purpose of prevention or health maintenance rather than treatment. (Rianto, 2017). Another problem is that the number of HAV operations so far is still very low. The following are some of the support operations and health services carried out by HAV:

Table 1: HAV Support and Service Activities

Year	No	Type of Operation	Location
2014	1	Ops Mentawai Megathrust (health services)	West Sumatera
	2	Ops SBJ LXIII/Sail Raja Ampat (health services)	West Papua
	3	Ops Bansos Bawean (health services)	East Java
2015	1	Ops Perisai Samor	Maluku and NTT
	2	Ops Social Service Banten and SAR Jakarta	Banten
	3	Ops Komodo Jaya & Jayapura (health services)	Papua and NTB
	4	Ops SBJ/LXIV & Sail Tomini (health services)	Gorontalo
	5	Ops Evacuation of South Kalimantan Haze Victims (health services)	South Kalimantan
2020	1	Ops for the evacuation of Indonesian citizens in Japan during the Covid-19 pandemic	Yokohama, Japan

Source: Journal of dr. Soeharso 990, 2020

Based on table above, it can be seen that the HAV operation only ranged from three to five times a year in the 2014-2015 period. Therefore, it can be said that the basic function as HAV in health services is still very minimal. By paying attention to the strategic environmental conditions related to geography and demography in current conditions, especially for the demands of the community for health service facilities with global standards, the problem of the Covid-19 pandemic, and the presence of military threats in the Natuna sea area, the optimization of the SDS that is urgent to be realized is in a more optimal form of HAV operation.

According to Corbett (1911), the sea can be strengthened by implementing a maritime power strategy, namely by maximizing the role of ships with the support of land forces. In accordance with this, increasing the operation of the HAV can be said to be a form of optimizing the SDS. As mentioned by Lykke (1998), that strategy formulation needs to refer to three main aspects, namely aspects of the goals to be achieved (ends), ways that can be applied to achieve these goals (ways), and the resources needed (means) to be able to take various ways to achieve goals.

Based on the overall explanation above, this research was carried out with the aim of analyzing and explaining the implementation of the SDS through the current HAV operation and analyzing and formulating the optimization of the SDS with the operation of the HAV in order to support national defense. The results obtained from this research

are expected to provide useful input for the development of SDS knowledge, especially those related to the operation of the HAV in supporting the optimization of SDS.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Strategy Theory

Definition of strategy according to Salusu (1996) is a decision pattern that is used with reference to the goals and objectives to be achieved, which is the basis for the emergence of various policies and plans in order to achieve these goals and objectives. Strategy has a scope that is used as a reference in determining and implementing various planned and targeted actions.

According to another point of view, Tangkilisan (2005) states that strategy is a form of reaction or response that an organization or institution has to face various challenges and demands that arise as a result of changes in the surrounding factors. The reaction or response is very important because it determines the success or failure of the organization to survive and thrive in the midst of changing environmental conditions. The right response will be a solid foundation for the growth of organizational strength. Conversely, if the response is not in accordance with the existing challenges or demands, the related organizations or institutions will be vulnerable to failure and destruction.

The formation of responses or reactions that are owned by organizations or institutions or government agencies is generally based on various factors that become the strength of the entity. Empowerment of all aspects of strength can be carried out effectively and efficiently if the parties who become the brain of the organization have superior abilities in formulating and planning strategy implementation, and coordinating strategies to all elements of the organization in order to create harmonious cooperation in the process of implementing the strategy (Tangkilisan, 2005).

Etymologically, strategy comes from the Greek "strategos" which is a combination of the words "stratos" (military) and "ag" (to lead), so that the word strategos can be interpreted as leadership, or various things that leaders do to achieve victory. in war. Based on this understanding, it can be seen that the term strategy is basically a term that is synonymous with the military world (Yunus, 2016).

In the military realm, the notion of strategy is explained by Lykke (1998) as "*the art and science of employing the armed forces of a nation to secure the objectives of national policy by the application of force or the threat of force.*" According to this definition, military strategy is a form of exploiting the power of the state to ensure that the stated goals can be achieved, so that the interests of the state can be fulfilled.

Strategy has three main components, namely the goals to be achieved (ends), actions or methods used to achieve goals (ways), and instruments that can be used to achieve goals (means). The strategic concept can be used as the basis for the formulation of military strategies, as well as strategies in other important fields (Lykke, 1998).

2.2 Optimization

Optimization is defined as an effort carried out with the aim of ensuring that the implementation of a plan can achieve all the objectives set and can minimize the impact of losses that may be caused during the process (Pratama, 2013). Based on this understanding, it can be concluded that optimization is a process of activity to improve and optimize a job to be more / fully perfect, functional, or more effective and to find the best solution of several problems in order to achieve the best possible goal according to certain criteria.

2.3 Policy Implementation

Public policy in the defense sector is an important factor that plays a role in the development of the national defense force. Policies can generate optimal benefits if implemented appropriately, by considering and fulfilling various factors that influence the implementation process. According to Prakoso (2016), those factors consist of Integrative, Interactive, Transparency, Controlling and Accountability (IITCA).

The first factor, namely integrative, is related to the need for integration between government agencies with an interest and a role in national defense development. The institution consists of the Ministry of Defense, TNI, ministries and other institutions, as well as various other defense components as stated in the 1945 Constitution article 30 regarding the rights and obligations of every citizen in an effort to defend the state.

The second factor, namely interactive, is a determining factor for the effectiveness of policy implementation. In accordance with Edward III's (1980) policy implementation model, policy implementation requires an interactive communication process, allowing the delivery of various important information between the parties implementing the policy. Interactive communication can also minimize rejection that occurs for policies that are implemented because of a complete understanding of the objectives to be achieved from the policy.

The third factor, namely transparency, is a factor related to the openness of the content and policy objectives to the public. This factor is very important to build public trust in the country and in the defense policy implemented. With transparency, the community can fulfill their need to be able to oversee the state. In general, transparency is concerned with planning, formulating and executing budgets.

The fourth factor, namely controlling, is a factor that determines the suitability between implementation and the policy plan. With supervision, various errors that occur during the implementation process can be detected immediately and the most appropriate solutions can be found, so that policy implementation can continue in a direction that is in accordance with the objectives to be achieved.

The last factor, namely accountability, is a factor that forms the main form of public trust in policies and institutions that are authorized to formulate and implement these policies. Accountability is the result of the implementation of responsibility, which can be achieved in line with the fulfillment of community needs for the benefits of all activities of government institutions carried out in the public interest. Accountability can be formed through the implementation of open outreach to the public who are the party that mandates government agencies in the defense force development process through the implementation of public policies in the defense sector.

Apart from referring to the factors above, the successful implementation of a policy also depends on public participation as the main stakeholder in public policy. Policy implementation, which is generally in the form of implementing programs compiled in accordance with the content of the policy, requires harmonious cooperation between policy implementers and the community so that policy goals and objectives can be achieved (Sunarti, 2016)

3. Research Methodology

This research is conducted using a phenomenological qualitative approach. The research was carried out at the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia, the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, the Indonesian Navy Headquarters, Komando Fleet I, KRI dr. Soeharso-990 and KRI Semarang-594.

The research data were obtained from interviews with research informants who were selected according to two criteria, namely: 1) Parties who have a deep understanding of sea defense strategies; and 2) Parties that have a direct or indirect relationship with HAV operations. Based on these criteria, the informants of this study were determined to consist of the Head of sub directorate the drafters of national defense policies Indonesian Defense Ministry, Secretary of the naval health service, directorate of health services and facilities Indonesian Health Ministry, Staff of sub-service of naval operations and training, Staff of 1st Naval Fleet, Commander of KRI dr. Soeharso-990 and Commander of KRI Semarang-594.

The results of interviews with informants were also supported by data from observations, documentation, and literature study. All of the data were analyzed using qualitative analysis techniques in five stages, namely data analysis, data reduction, data categorization, data validity, and data interpretation.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Overview of Hospital Auxiliary Vessels

Since January 7, 2021, Indonesia has had three HAV, namely KRI dr. Soeharso-990, KRI Semarang-594, and KRI dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo-991. The three HAV became the operational fleet of the Indonesian Navy which functioned both during war and peacetime. Operations during wartime are aimed at providing assistance to victims of war, while operations during peacetime are aimed at humanitarian missions, disaster management, and for certain other situations.

Indonesia's first HAV, namely KRI dr Soeharso-990, was designated as HAV on August 24, 2007 with reference to the Decree of the Chief of Staff of the Indonesian Navy (Kasal) Number Skep / 1100 / VIII / 2007. The function of KRI dr. Soeharso-990 is as a HAV with the ability as a level II hospital which is part of the Indonesian Eastern Region Fleet Command (Koarmada II) in the supporting forces. (Susdarwono, 2019).

The second HAV is KRI Semarang-594. The HAV was handed over from PT PAL Indonesia as the maker to the Indonesian Navy at the Ujung Koarmada II Pier in Surabaya on January 21, 2019. KRI Semarang-594 which is the Makassar Class LPD is a fleet that strengthens Koarmada I under the Amphibious Ship Unit with the main function of supporting the military material distribution process and also as HAV.

The third HAV owned by Indonesia is KRI Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo-991. Like KRI Semarang-594, KRI Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo-991 is a product of PT PAL Indonesia and handed over to the Indonesian Navy on January 7, 2021.

4.2 Implementation of Sea Defense Strategy through Operation of Hospital Auxiliary Vessel

The conceptual framework that becomes the analysis reference for the implementation of SDS in this study is the IITCA model proposed by Prakoso (2016), which states that there are five important factors that influence the implementation process, namely Integrative, Interactive, Transparency, Controlling and Accountability factors..

In the first factor, namely Integrative, the informants stated that the operation of HAV was the result of an agreement between the parties concerned. The Indonesian Navy is the organizer that operates the HAV according to the needs or requests of the Ministry that proposed the operation of the HAV. In practice, for example in a humanitarian mission in 2016 which was a collaboration between the Indonesian Ministry of Defense and the Indonesian Navy for the operation of KRI dr Soeharso to Timor Leste (Hermawan, 2016). Furthermore, on the KRI mission of Dr. Soheraso in picking up Indonesian citizens who were crew members of the Diamond Princess and World Dream cruise ships, the Indonesian Navy collaborated with the Ministry of Health to establish procedures for handling Indonesian citizens who are indicated to be affected by Covid-19 (Firman Mawero dan Anries Tanu Radena, 2020).

Regarding the second factor, namely interactive, the Indonesian Navy and related Ministries with an interest in the operational mission of HAV continue to carry out intense and interactive communication in order to fulfill mission needs and ensure that the realization of the mission is in accordance with the predetermined plan. Although in the interaction process it was said that there were no significant obstacles, in practice there were problems that caused the operation time to swell and exceed the plan. The root cause of the problem is the limited number of HAV used and in terms of the competence of the crew, so that the implementation of activities cannot be on time according to schedule. This can be overcome by determining a sufficient operational time span by considering the possibility of additional operating time that may occur, of course, must still refer to the target time and budget provided for

the mission to be carried out. In addition, in early January 2021 the KRI Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo-991 was inaugurated as the third HAV fleet, so it is hoped that the addition of the new HAV unit can overcome the problem of the existing HAV shortcomings.

Regarding the third factor, namely transparency, especially transparency regarding the HAV operating budget, so far there have never been any problems that stem from the lack of transparency in the HAV operating budget. This is the result of intense and interactive communication regarding the issue, as well as the existence of trust between interested parties, namely between the Indonesian Navy and related Ministries.

The fourth factor that affects the implementation of SDS in the form of HAV operations is controlling the operation of HAV on each mission. In accordance with the opinion of the research informants, it can be seen that the control of the HAV operation is in the hands of fleet command and the Headquarters of the supervision to ensure that every mission carried out by HAV succeeds in achieving its goals effectively and efficiently (interview Muhammad Taufik, 2021). In accordance with the success of the implementation of the various HAV missions as previously explained, it can be said that there are no fundamental problems related to control factors. In that sense, all the objectives of the mission carried out by HAV can be achieved properly. However, it is necessary to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the process in order to avoid increasing the operational time of the HAV because it can lead to an increase in the budget and not meeting other HAV operating targets.

Furthermore, it relates to the last factor, namely accountability, or the responsibility of all parties involved in the operation of HAV. In accordance with the opinions of the informants, it can be seen that there are no problems related to the accountability of parties related to the operation of HAV. Both the Navy as the organizer and the relevant Ministries as the determinants of the mission carried out in the operation of the HAV have carried out their respective responsibilities well. This can be seen in the fulfillment of the material and personnel of the HAV crews. The Indonesian Navy provides for the HAV crew, while the Ministry of Health determines medical personnel to provide health services. Likewise with the Ministry of Defense which coordinates with friendly countries which are the targets of cross-border humanitarian missions. The implementation of the responsibilities of each of these parties is the main basis for the successful operation of the HAV which is part of the Indonesian SDS.

Apart from the need to pay attention to the five factors according to the IITCA concept developed by Prakoso (2016), there are actually other important factors that need to be considered as their influence on the policy implementation process of the SDS, namely the affordability factor or the ability of the Indonesian Navy to make purchases of various resources or facilitate the entire implementation process.

The affordability factor can be said to be a determinant of the smooth implementation process because without the ability to meet the various resource needs needed in implementation, the implementation objectives will be difficult to achieve. Integration, interactivity, transparency, control and accountability do have a major influence on the implementation of SDS through the operation of HAV. However, all of these factors ultimately depend on the affordability factor of the Indonesian Navy which refers to the availability of the defense budget set by the government.

4.3 Optimization of Sea Defense Strategy through Operation of Hospital Auxiliary Vessels

Basically, the implementation of the SDS by operating the HAV can be carried out quite well, which can be seen in the achievement of several goals and objectives of each mission carried out. This can also be seen from the lack of problems stemming from the main factors affecting the implementation process, both in terms of integration between related parties, established communication, budget transparency, controlling the HAV operation process, as well as the accountability of all parties interested in operating HAV. However, in accordance with the conditions of Indonesia's maritime security which still cannot be said to be safe and stable due to the various real threats faced, it is necessary to optimize the SDS which in the context of this research is specified with the operation of the HAV.

The strategy formulated to optimize SDS used in this study refers to the three components of the strategy proposed by Lykke (1998), namely the goals to be achieved (ends), methods or ways that can be applied to achieve these goals (ways), and resources required (means) to achieve the goal. These three components are interrelated with one another in forming a strategy that is directed, applicable, and rational in nature.

In relation to the first component, namely the ends (objectives) of the SDS optimization strategy, the informants stated several proposed objectives for the operation of the HAV. First, optimization can be done by ensuring that the operational objectives of the HAV have actually facilitated the entire scope of objectives as stipulated in the Technical Guidelines for Hospital Assistance Ship Support, which is linked to the Decree of the Chief of Staff of the Navy Number: Kep / 2 / II / 2006 concerning The Strategic Policy of the Chief of Navy Staff in Realizing the Posture of the Indonesian Navy until 2024, and integrated with the support for 14 TNI duties in MOOTW as stipulated in Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning TNI.

Regarding the development of its objectives, HAV in addition to carrying out humanitarian missions in the form of providing health services to people in remote and outermost islands of Indonesia, can also carry out a mission of strengthening the commitment to defend the state from the community which is a national resource in the universal defense system. In addition, the intense interaction between the HAV crew and the community in the target area can also be used to gather important information that is useful for increasing awareness of the efforts of foreign parties who try to enter or interfere with state sovereignty in the border area.

In addition, it can also be developed through the establishment of a routine operating schedule by considering the target area according to the level of need for medical services and the need for gathering important information related to the activities of foreign parties in Indonesia's maritime border areas. HAV operation with reference to this goal will be able to strengthen sea defense in terms of information and increase the commitment of coastal communities to participate in efforts to defend the country.

Furthermore, in relation to the second strategy component, namely the ways of the strategy to optimize the SDS with the operation of the HAV, the informants stated that the method for being able to achieve the various objectives set out to optimize the SDS was that the Indonesian Navy proposed to the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia to add new HAV units for increasing the ability of assistance support, proposing an increase in the number of human resources, in this case the HAV crew, and striving to improve the competence of the HAV crew (interview with Muhammad Taufik, 2021), as well as analyzing potential non-military threats for prevention and response by empowering the main components consisting of Ministries and other non-military institutions, as well as all national resources (community) which are classified as other elements of state defense from non-military threats (interview Sugeng Suryanto).

Furthermore, with regard to the third strategy component, namely the means or resources needed to achieve the objectives of the strategy to optimize SDS with the operation of HAV, the informants mentioned the determination of their own units or departments that are a permanent part of the HAV for the provision of health services; the appointment of a permanent man for HAV; as well as determining a budget in accordance with the operational needs of the HAV. These various resources need to be provided in sufficient quantity and quality as needed in order to optimize SDS by operating the HAV.

In terms of adding resources, it is very important to pay attention to the affordability aspects of these resources. Affordability comes from the word affordable, which means it can be purchased because of its affordable price. Thus, affordability means the nature of something that is possible to buy because of its affordability. A thing is said to be affordable to buy after a comparison between price and purchasing power is made, so that affordability and purchasing power are two things that cannot be separated (Jauhari & Manaf, 2014).

In the context of this research, the affordability aspect of various types of resources that need to be procured in order to optimize the SDS through the operation of the HAV needs to refer to the purchasing power of the Indonesian Navy and the defense budget set by the government. The analysis of the suitability between

affordability and purchasing power of the Indonesian Navy can refer to the concept of Military Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) proposed by Melese et al. (2018).

Based on the discussion that has been done regarding the optimization of the SDS with the operation of the HAV in order to support national defense, a common thread that connects this optimization strategy with one of the strategies in the MDSN, namely the Sea Control Strategy can be drawn. According to Mustari et al. (2018), the Sea Control Strategy is a strategy to ensure the use of the sea for Indonesia's national interests and prevent other parties / opponents from using the sea for their interests. As an implication, the value of sea control is to allow one's own use of the sea to protect resources in peacetime and prevent other parties / enemies from using the sea for their own interests. The application of the sea control strategy is carried out in accordance with the comparison of the relative strength with the opponent's strength, time and place limitations, and the objectives of the sea control itself. Operationally, sea control can be carried out offensively or defensively through various tactical actions in joint operations that use components of TNI forces in an integrated manner.

Through an emphasis on sea control strategies, strategy optimization is manifested in the implementation of the MOTW which aims to increase support from Indonesian people living in remote and outermost areas for efforts to safeguard the country's sovereignty. This can be achieved by carrying out regular interaction and guidance to communities in the region as part of a humanitarian mission in terms of providing health facilities.

In practice, as an activity in a sea control strategy, the higher the intention and efforts to defend the state from people living in outermost and remote areas, the output obtained from the implementation of the HAV mission is in the form of more information that can be collected for monitoring needs of border areas. The more surveillance is carried out based on information obtained from the communities around the border, the higher the achievement of efforts to uphold state sovereignty in the form of guaranteeing the use of the sea for national interests and preventing foreign parties from using the sea for their own interests.

Optimization of SDS through the operation of the HAV proposed by researchers still refers to the provisions in Article 22 of the Geneva Convention II of 1949 and Article 1 of the Hague Convention (X) 1907. Efforts to collect information and increase community commitment in coastal and outer areas are purely for the purpose of national defense development and carried out in peaceful conditions. This should be distinguished from the use of medical vessels for spying and military advantage as prohibited in Article 22 of the Geneva Convention II of 1949 and Article 1 of the Hague Convention (X) 1907.

5. Conclusion

Conclusions that can be drawn based on the discussions that have been carried out are as follows:

1. The implementation of the SDS through the operation of the HAV in order to support national defense in accordance with the IITCA policy implementation model was carried out quite well, but was still not optimal because there were several obstacles that were found. These constraints consisted of the insufficient number of HAV; readiness as well as the quantity of its crew. In addition, HAV operations are still carried out with reference to situational requests or needs from other Ministries (Ministry of Health and Ministry of Defense), and do not yet have regular schedules or regular programs for humanitarian missions and health services to communities in coastal and outermost areas.
2. Optimizing SDS through the operation of HAV in order to support national defense proposed by researchers is to focus on the Sea Control Strategy. The strategy is structured based on an analysis of the three components of the strategy, namely ends, ways and means.

Suggestions that can be submitted based on the research conclusions are as follows:

1. The Ministry of Defense needs to make efforts to increase the number of HAV units to reach the ideal number needed by Indonesia. The addition of HAV units can be considered in terms of the affordability of the units produced by PT PAL Indonesia which are compared with the benefits that can be obtained from the addition of these units, both benefits for improving national defense and other benefits that can be felt directly by the community..

2. The Indonesian Navy, which plays a direct role in the operation of the HAV, needs to have a definite concept in determining the ideal number of HAV needs and how long it will take to fulfill the HAV needs in accordance with the state defense budget capacity, and prepare the formulation and establishment of a more effective HAV operational Technical Manual.
3. The integration between the Ministry of Health and the Indonesian Navy is the basis for the current operation of the HAV. Therefore, the Ministry of Health needs to improve coordination with the Indonesian Navy, especially regarding the making of regular schedules or fixed programs every year using HAV. This is needed so that the nature of the HAV operation is no longer situational, but rather an activity that is routinely carried out as part of the national defense system.

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